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3 **Assessing the Susceptibility of Olive Cultivars to Anthracnose Caused by**
4 ***Colletotrichum acutatum***

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13 **ABSTRACT**

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17 Selected olive cultivars were tested in the field and laboratory for their relative
18 susceptibility to anthracnose caused by *Colletotrichum acutatum*. A rating scale to
19 assess fruit-rot incidence in naturally infected trees was validated by comparing ratings
20 with direct counts of affected fruit. Fruit-rot incidence varied greatly among twenty
21 cultivars and was correlated with the severity of branch dieback symptoms that
22 developed after fruit-rot epidemics. For determining whether artificial inoculation can
23 be used to predict anthracnose susceptibility in the orchard, detached fruit of twelve
24 cultivars were inoculated with *C. acutatum* and fruit-rot severity was assessed
25 periodically. Progress of disease severity over time fit the logistic function for all

1 cultivars. The best correlation between fruit-rot incidence in the field and disease
2 severity on inoculated fruit was obtained using a disease susceptibility index that
3 integrated the maximum disease progress rate and the estimated time to reach 50% of
4 disease severity. Based on field observations and laboratory data on susceptibility to
5 anthracnose, 21 cultivars were classified into three groups: highly susceptible
6 (Cornicabra, Hojiblanca, Lechín de Sevilla, Manzanilla de Sevilla, Morona, Ocal,
7 Picudo, and Verdial de Huévar); moderately susceptible (Arbequina, Arbosana, Morrut,
8 Pajarero, and Villalonga); and resistant (Blanqueta, Empeltre, Frantoio, Koroneiki,
9 Leccino, Morona-D, Picual, and Razzola).

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11 Additional Keywords: aceituna jabonosa, *Colletotrichum gloeosporioides*,
12 *Gloeosporium olivarum*, *Olea europaea*, resistance.

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14 The Spanish olive industry presently comprises over 2.5 million ha with an
15 annual olive oil production value exceeding 2.8 billion euros in the last 4 years (16).
16 More than 65% of Spanish olive production is concentrated in the Andalusian region of
17 southern Spain, where olive trees are an essential element of the landscape and form a
18 mosaic of cultivars (27).

19 Anthracnose of olive (*Olea europaea* L.), caused by the fungi *Colletotrichum*
20 *acutatum* J. H. Simmonds and *C. gloeosporioides* (Penz.) Penz. & Sacc., is the most
21 destructive disease of olive fruit and is widely distributed in many olive-growing
22 regions of the world (8, 13, 29). In Spain, the disease is named for its characteristic
23 fruit-rot and mummification syndrome, with abundant production of conidia in a
24 gelatinous matrix (“aceituna jabonosa” or “soapy fruit”) under wet conditions (8, 18). In
25 recent epidemics in southern Spain, affected trees showed wilting of leaves and dieback

1 of shoots and branches, besides the characteristic fruit-rot syndrome (2, 32). All isolates
2 of *Colletotrichum* causing olive anthracnose in these epidemics in Andalusia were
3 identified as *C. acutatum* (21, 25).

4 The severity the incidence of anthracnose in Andalusia d depends greatly on
5 cultivar susceptibility and weather, severe epidemics only occur under favorable
6 weather conditions in areas where susceptible cultivars are grown, such as in the south
7 of Córdoba, north of Málaga-Sevilla, and west of Granada provinces.

8 The dominant cultivars in these areas are ‘Hojiblanca’ and ‘Picudo’, which are
9 highly susceptible to anthracnose (2). A similar situation occurs in wet regions of
10 Portugal, where the susceptible cv. Galega vulgar is grown (29). Fortunately, the most
11 important cultivar in Andalusia, ‘Picual’, is considered resistant to anthracnose under
12 field conditions, although a moderate level of disease occurs when ‘Picual’ trees are
13 grown in a mixture with susceptible cultivars (32).

14 Information on the susceptibility or resistance to anthracnose in olive cultivars is
15 based on field observations and farmer experience rather than on systematic studies. To
16 characterize resistance levels, researchers have artificially inoculated fruit or plants only
17 in a few cases and with variable results (12, 18). A related problem is that olive
18 cultivars are frequently misidentified in the field (2). For these reasons, discrepancies
19 about resistance or susceptibility to anthracnose for some olive cultivars are quite
20 common (20, 21). An example of these discrepancies is the database of olive germplasm
21 (3), which includes two cultivars each with two different levels of susceptibility to
22 anthracnose. Another source of confusion is the similarity of fruit-rot symptoms caused
23 by other fungal pathogens, such as species of *Alternaria*, *Botryosphaeria*, *Fusarium*,
24 and *Phlyctema* (2, 9, 11, 22).

1 The need to determine the relative susceptibility of olive cultivars to anthracnose
2 became more evident after the establishment of the Olive World Germplasm Bank
3 (OWGB) and the beginning of an olive breeding program in Córdoba, southern Spain
4 (6, 27). The demand to assess a great number of olive cultivars and genotypes and the
5 lack of a suitable method for their evaluation led us to develop an inoculation method to
6 quantify resistance to *Colletotrichum* spp. (21) and to carry out the present work. The
7 objectives of this study were (i) to develop a method to assess the susceptibility of a
8 large number of olive cultivars and genotypes to anthracnose caused by *Colletotrichum*
9 spp. and (ii) to evaluate the relative susceptibility of selected cultivars. A preliminary
10 report of this study has been published (24).

11

12 **MATERIALS AND METHODS**

13

14 **Orchards.** Three experimental orchards of different olive cultivars were
15 selected; two were located in Córdoba and one in Jaén, Andalusian provinces in
16 southern Spain. The three orchards belong to the Andalusian Institute for Research and
17 Formation in Agriculture and Fishery (IFAPA in Spanish). The first orchard (“Alameda
18 del Obispo”) was selected as a part of the Olive World Germplasm Bank (OWGB),
19 which is located at the IFAPA Centre of Córdoba. The OWGB was planted in several
20 stages starting in 1982, and in 2005 it contained 406 cultivars (6). For this study, twenty
21 cultivars ranging from high to low susceptibility to anthracnose were selected in the first
22 orchard. There were four replicated trees per cultivar in a completely randomized
23 design. The second orchard (“La Mina”) was an experimental site located at the IFAPA
24 Centre of Cabra in Córdoba. Trees were planted in 1987, and there were 12 olive
25 cultivars replicated 12 times in a complete block design, with one tree of each cultivar

1 per block. The third orchard (“Venta del Llano”) was part of an experimental collection
2 of olive cultivars located at the IFAPA Centre of Mengíbar in Jaén. Trees were planted
3 in 1987, and there were 19 cultivars, with at least two replicated trees per cultivar in a
4 completely randomized design.

5 Experimental orchards were managed according to the principles of commercial
6 olive orchards in Andalusia (2, 7). Each tree had been planted in a 7×7 m square, with
7 one trunk per tree, and was pruned every 3 years after the fifth year of planting. Several
8 copper-based treatments (copper sulphate, 7.5 kg Cu per hectare) were applied during
9 the spring and autumn to control fungal foliar and fruit diseases caused by *Fusicladium*
10 *oleagineum*, *Pseudocercospora cladosporioides*, and *Colletotrichum* spp. (2, 7).

11 **Assessment of disease incidence in the field.** Incidence of anthracnose was
12 assessed in each olive tree by estimating the percentage of affected fruit using a 0 to 10
13 rating scale. In each tree, the assessor circled the canopy looking for affected fruit in a 1
14 to 2 m band above the ground. The area checked was approximately 1/8 (12.5%) of the
15 total canopy. The assessment took about 1 to 2 min, depending on the total number of
16 fruit per tree. In a previous study, we estimated that this number varied between 4,000
17 and 20,000 fruit, so observed fruit per tree varied between 500 and 2,500. Trees with
18 heavy fruit load had small-sized fruit that ripened slowly, making more difficult the
19 assessment of anthracnose incidence. In general, fruit were assessed while still attached
20 to the tree, but in some cases the assessment included fallen fruit on the soil surface.

21 The rating scale used derived from the logistic growth of the epidemic and the
22 binary nature of the data. If p_i is the proportion of affected fruit in the time i , $1-p_i$ is the
23 proportion of healthy fruit at this time. The expression $\frac{p_i}{1-p_i}$ is called the odds, and the

24 quotient between two consecutive odds ($\frac{odds_{i+1}}{odds_i}$) is called the odds ratio (OR). The OR

1 is a constant characteristic of each sigmoid curve. Making OR = 3, we obtained the
 2 sigmoid curve in Figure 1, which shows the relationship between the rating scale values
 3 (0 to 10) and the proportion (0 to 1), or percentage (0 to 100%), of affected fruit. An
 4 increase of one scale unit corresponds to a three-time increase in the odds that fruit are
 5 affected. The equation for this curve is:

$$6 \quad p = \frac{1}{1 + 3^{(7-n)}}$$

7 where p is the proportion of affected fruit and n is the rating scale value. The scale value
 8 of 7 corresponds to the proportion $p = 0.5$ or 50% of affected fruit. This is the inflexion
 9 point of the logistic curve. This value is arbitrary, and it was selected by taking into
 10 account the initial value of proportion of affected fruit (p_1):

$$11 \quad p_1 = \frac{1}{1 + 3^{(7-1)}} = \frac{1}{730} = 0.14\%$$

12 Because the mean number of observed fruit per tree varied between 500 and
 13 2500, the rating scale 1 and its interval included a mean incidence of one affected fruit
 14 per tree, which varied from 0.04% to 0.20% ($\frac{1}{2500}$ to $\frac{1}{500}$). Mean values of p and their
 15 intervals for each rating scale value are indicated in Figure 1 and Table 1. Extreme
 16 values of the rating scale corresponded to $p_0 < 0.04\%$ and $p_{10} > 94\%$. Besides the entire
 17 rating scale values from 0 to 10, intermediate values (0.5) also were used when there
 18 was some doubt between two consecutive scale values. To facilitate the use of the scale
 19 in the field, the three lower rating scale values were described as follows: 0 = no
 20 affected fruit per tree, 1 = one to three affected fruit per tree, 2 = one to three affected
 21 fruit per each quarter of the tree canopy. Numbers one to three of affected fruit
 22 depended mainly on the tree harvest. Whereas ratings of 0, 1 or 2 depended on the
 23 number of affected fruit per tree, higher rating values were obtained by estimating the
 24 percentage of affected fruit per tree (Table 1).

1 The relationship between the proportion of affected fruit (Y) and rating scale
2 values (X) can be also expressed as:

$$3 \quad Y = \frac{1}{1 + 3^{(7-X)}} = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-\ln 3(X-7)}} = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-aX+b}}$$

4 which is the regular equation for the logistic model, making $a = \ln(3) = 1.099$ and $b =$
5 $7 \cdot \ln(3) = 7.69$ for this particular case. This relationship also can be formulated using the

6 logit transformation [$\text{logit}(Y) = \ln \frac{Y}{1-Y} = aX + b = \ln 3 \times (X - 7)$]. Solving for X , we

7 get the relationship between the rating scale values (X) and the logit of proportion of
8 affected fruit (Y):

$$9 \quad X = \frac{1}{\ln 3} \times \ln \frac{Y}{1-Y} + 7$$

10 This equation shows that scale values are a linear function of the logit of proportion of
11 affected fruit.

12 To validate the 0-10 rating scale in the field, we selected a total of 55 affected
13 trees, five trees per each scale value, from different cultivars in the three experimental
14 orchards. After they were assessed using the rating scale, trees were harvested and 2500
15 fruit from each tree were randomly selected and evaluated for unequivocal symptoms of
16 anthracnose.

17 **Disease incidence on selected cultivars in the experimental orchards.** A total
18 of 20 olive cultivars were selected in the three experimental orchards to assess the
19 incidence of fruit rot using the 0-10 rating scale (Table 2). All cultivars are considered
20 native to Spain except Frantoio and Razzola, which are native to Italy, and Koroneiki,
21 which is native to Greece (1). Disease incidence was assessed at different times, when
22 most fruit of each cultivar had become black or had the value 4 in the 0 to 4 rating scale
23 for olive fruit ripening (27). Disease incidence was assessed from the end of November

1 to the end of January in 1997/98, 2005/06, and 2006/07. There were severe epidemics of
2 olive anthracnose in the experimental orchards during these years.

3 In the La Mina orchard, severity of branch dieback (BD) was evaluated by the
4 end of March 2007, after 2 years of fruit-rot epidemics. BD severity was assessed using
5 a 0 to 5 rating scale based on the percentage of tree canopy affected: 0 < 10%, 1 = 10–
6 25%, 2 = 25–50%, 3 = 50–75%, 4 = 75–90%, 5 = > 90%. The presence of
7 *Colletotrichum* spp. in affected branches was evaluated culturing small pieces of tissue
8 on PDA plus 100 mg of cooper sulphate according to Moral *et al.* (23).

9 **Inoculation of detached fruit.** Olive fruit of 11 cultivars (Table 3) were
10 collected at the onset of ripening from healthy trees in orchards located in Córdoba and
11 Jaén provinces in 2006/07. The fruit were green-yellow and with a value of 1 on the 0-4
12 ripening scale except for fruit from cv. Picual. Two samples of cv. Picual differing in
13 fruit ripeness were used: ‘Picual-G’ had green-yellow fruit (ripening stage 1) and
14 ‘Picual-M’ had violet fruit (ripening stage 3). The cultivar initially identified, as
15 ‘Morona’ was later considered different from cv. Morona grown at OWGB of Córdoba
16 based on morphological characters, and now it is being identified by molecular analysis
17 (D. Barranco, University of Cordoba, Spain, *personal communication*). For this reason,
18 this unknown cultivar has been labelled as ‘Morona-D’.

19 Inoculations were performed with the isolate Col-10 of *C. acutatum*, which is
20 representative of the Spanish population of the pathogen causing olive anthracnose (25).
21 Fruit were washed, disinfested, inoculated (by sprayed with a suspension of 10^5 conidia
22 per ml) and incubated as previously reported (21).. Disease severity was assessed every
23 2 to 3 days after inoculation by using a previously described scale from 0 to 5 (21)..
24 There were two replicates (moisture chambers) per treatment and 25 fruit per replicate
25 arranged in a completely randomized design. The experiment was performed twice.

1 **Statistical analysis.** To validate the 1 to 10 rating scale, observed scale values
2 (X) for each tree were transformed into percentage of affected fruit (Y) by using the logit
3 transformation indicated earlier. Logit transformed values were regressed against the
4 percentage of affected fruit obtained after counting anthracnose affected fruit in a
5 sample of 2500 fruit collected from each tree. Linear regression was performed using a
6 model forced through the origin and considering the significance of the regression,
7 coefficient of determination (R^2), coefficient of determination adjusted for degrees of
8 freedom (R_a^2), and pattern of residuals over logit transformed and fitted values.

9 Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed on the rating scale data of
10 incidence of fruit rot and branch dieback severity in selected olive cultivars because
11 these data satisfied the normality and homogeneity of variances requirements of
12 ANOVA. Cultivar means were compared using Tukey's Honestly Significant
13 Difference (HSD) test at $P = 0.05$. The relationship between incidence of fruit rot and
14 branch dieback severity was analyzed by the Pearson's correlation test.

15 Disease severity values of inoculated fruit were used to calculate a Disease
16 Intensity Index (DII) using the following formula:

$$17 \quad DII = \frac{\sum n_i \times i}{5 \times N} \times 100$$

18 where i represents severity (0 to 5), n_i is the number of fruit with the severity of i , and N
19 is the total number of evaluated fruit. For each cultivar and repetition, the standardized
20 area under the disease progress curve (SAUDPC) was calculated by trapezoidal
21 integration of DII values over time expressed as a percentage of a maximum theoretical
22 curve. The SAUDPCs was transformed to $\arcsin \sqrt{SAUDPC/100}$ when necessary for
23 homogeneity of variance. ANOVA was performed on the SAUDPC data, and treatment
24 means were compared using Tukey's HSD test at $P = 0.05$. Curves of DII over time

1 were adjusted to the logistic model. For each adjusted curve, two representative
2 parameters were calculated: the time in days from inoculation to the inflexion point, and
3 the slope of the curve at this point. The first parameter represents the estimated time
4 (ET) necessary to reach 50% DII (ET₅₀), whereas the second parameter is the maximum
5 disease progress rate (MDPR). Means of ET₅₀ and MDPR were compared using
6 Tukey's HSD test at $P = 0.05$. Data from all experiments were analyzed using Statistix
7 8 (Analytical Software, Tallahassee, FL).

8

9 **RESULTS**

10

11 **Validation of rating scale.** The observed incidence of olive fruit affected by
12 anthracnose (based on a sample of 2,500 harvested fruit per tree) and the predicted
13 incidence (based on the logistic curve and the rating scale values previously estimated
14 in the same trees) were similar (Fig. 2A). Linear regression of observed values
15 expressed as percentages of affected fruit over the predicted values derived from the
16 logistic transformation of the rating scale values was highly significant ($P < 0.0001$),
17 with $R^2 = 0.9930$, $R_a^2 = 0.9928$, and a random pattern of residuals over logit
18 transformed and fitted values (Fig. 2B).

19 **Susceptibility of cultivars in the field.** Incidence of fruit rot on selected
20 cultivars in the field varied greatly among orchards and years (Table 2). The most
21 severe anthracnose epidemic occurred in the Alameda del Obispo orchard in 1997/98,
22 whereas the lowest levels of disease occurred in the Venta del Llano orchard in
23 2006/07. Trees in the latter orchard were only evaluated in 2006/07 because of the
24 generally low level of infection in other years. Similarly, trees in the La Mina orchard
25 were not evaluated in 1997/98 because they had a low level of infection. Cultivar

1 reaction ranged continuously from highly susceptible to highly resistant. The most
2 susceptible cultivar in all orchards was ‘Ocal’; other highly susceptible cultivars were
3 ‘Picudo’, ‘Hojiblanca’, ‘Manzanilla de Sevilla’, ‘Morona’, ‘Lechín de Sevilla’, and
4 ‘Cornicabra’. The most resistant cultivars were ‘Razzola’ and ‘Frantoio’; other cultivars
5 with a low level of susceptibility were ‘Koroneiki’, ‘Leccino’, and ‘Empeltre’. The
6 reactions of the remaining cultivars were less consistent among orchards and years,
7 although there were significant differences among them (Table 2).

8 In the La Mina orchard, the mean value of branch dieback severity (scale 0 to 5)
9 varied significantly among cultivars and was highly correlated ($r = 0.846$, $P < 0.0001$)
10 with the average fruit-rot incidence for each cultivar (Fig. 3). The pathogen *C. acutatum*
11 was isolated from $< 3\%$ of the sampled leaves, shoots, and branches with dieback
12 symptoms.

13 **Susceptibility of cultivars in artificial inoculation.** All cultivars developed
14 fruit-rot anthracnose symptoms at the end of the experiment, 84 days after inoculation.
15 Disease incidence and severity varied greatly with cultivar and time. The time of
16 appearance for the first symptom varied from 5 days after inoculation in the most
17 susceptible cultivar (‘Ocal’) to 45 days in the most resistant (‘Razzola’). Complete fruit
18 rot required as little as 21 days (‘Hojiblanca’ and ‘Ocal’) to more than 84 days
19 (‘Razzola’ and ‘Koroneiki’) because many fruit of the latter cultivars did not show
20 symptoms at the end of the experiment. For each cultivar, three disease development
21 times were calculated by interpolation: T_0 = days from inoculation until the first fruit
22 with symptoms appeared, T_{50} = days from inoculation until 50% of the fruit were
23 affected, and T_{100} = days from inoculation until 100% of the fruit were affected (Table
24 3). The SAUDPC analysis separated the cultivars into seven groups, although there was
25 overlap among cultivars (Table 3). Disease progress curves of DII for each cultivar were

1 well described by the logistic model (Fig. 4). The two representative parameters of these
2 curves, ET_{50} and MDP, determined several susceptibility groups of cultivars (Table
3 3), although these groups differed according to the parameter used for comparison. For
4 this reason, a new parameter (disease susceptibility index, DSI) was defined to integrate
5 both parameters. DSI was calculated as:

$$6 \quad DSI = \frac{MDP}{ET_{50}}$$

7 and it shows that cultivar susceptibility is directly proportional to the maximum disease
8 progress rate and inversely proportional to the time to reach 50% of DII. Means of DSI
9 were used to classify cultivars into five susceptibility groups (Table 3). Because DII
10 data had a good fit to the logistic function, an alternative data analysis was the
11 covariance of transformed data with the logit function $\left[\ln\left(\frac{DII}{100 - DII}\right) \right]$ using time as a
12 covariable. Comparison of DII means estimated by covariance analysis established eight
13 groups of cultivars based on susceptibility (Table 3).

14 The two samples of cv. Picual significantly differed in susceptibility. Picual-G
15 (ripening stage 1) had a low level of disease, while Picual-V (ripening stage 3) was
16 severely affected.

17

18 **Comparison between cultivar response in the field and after artificial**
19 **inoculation.** For 12 cultivars, susceptibility based on artificial inoculation and
20 susceptibility based on field observations were compared by correlating each variable
21 measured in the artificial inoculation with the average disease incidence observed in the
22 orchard (Table 3). The correlation coefficients for the different variables were low and
23 some were not significant (Table 4). The lack of correlation was mainly due to
24 discrepancies in two cvs.: Morona and Picudo. The correlation substantially increased

1 when both these cultivars were eliminated from the analysis. Without these two
2 cultivars, the best linear correlation was obtained with the variable DSI (Table 4). The
3 correlation between the variable DSI and the average of anthracnose incidence in the
4 remaining 10 cultivars, after elimination of ‘Morona’ and ‘Picudo’, is illustrated in
5 Figure 5.

6 7 **DISCUSSION**

8
9 Olive is the most extensively cultivated fruit crop in the world (10), and its great
10 intra-specific diversity is the key to its good adaptation to the many different areas with
11 a Mediterranean climate. Although olives are grown worldwide, the Mediterranean
12 basin is the major cultivation area, comprising about 98% of olive trees and more than
13 1200 cultivars (3). About 25% of all olive trees are grown in Spain, where the number
14 of well-identified cultivars is 272 (27). Variability of olive cultivars is being studied in
15 102 collections from 54 countries including 5,356 accessions (3). In part because there
16 are so many cultivars and many poorly identified cultivars, information on susceptibility
17 or resistance to major diseases is limited, particularly in the case of olive anthracnose
18 (2). Until the present study, little or no information was available on methods to assess
19 cultivars for their susceptibility to anthracnose under field and controlled conditions.

20 A parameter useful for assessing disease susceptibility under field conditions is
21 disease incidence, which is calculated by counting the number of diseased fruit in a
22 sample of detached fruit and expressing the count as the proportion or percentage of
23 total fruit. Assessing disease incidence is relatively straightforward, but it becomes
24 more difficult when the number of experimental units (trees) is large. In this case, it is
25 necessary to use other assessment methods, such as a rating scale to estimate the

1 incidence of affected fruit (17). The current study required a rapid method for assessing
2 disease incidence because of the great number of olive cultivars in some collections and
3 of the need to make several assessments as the olives ripened; several assessments were
4 necessary because of the rapid progress of anthracnose epidemics (2) and because
5 cultivars ripen at different times (21, 27). To obtain rapid and useful assessments, we
6 developed a rating scale to estimate the incidence of affected fruit in a tree. The scale is
7 based on the binary nature of data and the logistic growth of the epidemics. It is a pre-
8 transformed scale (14) in which binary data, expressed as the proportion of affected fruit
9 (Y), are normalized by applying the logit transformation of proportion $[\ln \frac{Y}{1-Y}]$.
10 Because the transformed scale data are normally distributed, they can be directly
11 subjected to analysis of variance and other parametric analyses. This rating scale is
12 close to the Horsfall-Barratt scale (17), but it differed from that one because its
13 adjustment to the logistic function.

14 The rating scale was validated in the field using olive trees of several cultivars
15 with a disease incidence from 0 to 100%. Scale values were well correlated ($r = 0.993$,
16 $P < 0.0001$) with data from direct counts in samples of olive fruit from the same trees.
17 Because we used at least 2,500 fruit per tree to obtain the count data, the latter are taken
18 to be the actual or true disease incidence values. The highly significant correlation
19 indicates a good agreement (accuracy) between estimated data (rating scale) and real
20 data (direct counts). Therefore, we conclude that scale values are useful to assess
21 disease incidence in different cultivars with different levels of disease. The main
22 advantage of using a disease incidence scale was that it saved time. Ratings using the
23 disease incidence scale required only 1 to 2 min per tree, whereas direct counts required
24 20 to 30 min per tree.

1 Twenty olive cultivars were assessed for susceptibility to anthracnose using the
2 disease incidence scale under field conditions. Susceptibility differed greatly among
3 cultivars, some of which were highly susceptible (with more than 75% of fruit affected,
4 e.g., ‘Ocal’, ‘Picudo’ or ‘Hojiblanca’) while others were highly resistant (with less than
5 1% of affected fruit, e.g., ‘Razzola’, ‘Frantoio’, or ‘Koroneiki’). There also were great
6 differences among orchards and years, with the highest disease incidence at the
7 Alameda del Obispo orchard in 1997/98 and the lowest disease incidence at the Venta
8 del Llano orchard in 2006/07. The ranking of cultivars, however, did not change
9 markedly with location or year, suggesting a dominant effect of genotype over the
10 environment (weather, pathogen population, level of disease). The main exception was
11 the Venta del Llano orchard in 2006/07, where the low level of disease did not permit a
12 separation of many cultivars because there were few or no affected fruit on the trees.

13 A major limitation for assessing cultivar susceptibility was the different ripeness
14 times. Because the susceptibility of fruit to anthracnose increases with ripeness (18, 21),
15 the date of assessment varied with the cultivar, and disease was assessed when most
16 fruit of each cultivar had become black, i.e, had a value of 4 on the olive ripening scale
17 (27). Besides cultivar misidentification, the lack of a uniform time for disease
18 assessment related to olive maturation may be the main cause for discrepancies among
19 published data on cultivar susceptibility (21). Information on cultivar susceptibility to
20 anthracnose under field conditions is limited. For example, the olive database contains
21 data for only 53 cultivars, which are classified by their susceptibility to anthracnose as
22 low (seven cultivars), medium (15 cultivars), and high (29 cultivars), as well as two
23 cultivars showing some discrepancies (3). Our field assessments agree with previous
24 observations for susceptible cvs. Arbequina, Blanqueta, Hojiblanca, Manzanilla de
25 Sevilla, Morrut, Ocal, and Picudo, and for the resistant or moderately resistant cultivars

1 Empeltre, Leccino, and Picual (1, 3, 8, 21, 27, 30). Cultivar Frantoio had low
2 susceptibility in our assessments, which agrees with some other observations (3, 19),
3 but it was considered susceptible in Argentina (8), possibly due to a misidentification of
4 the cultivar (1). Our results are also the first report of anthracnose susceptibility under
5 field conditions for cvs. Arbosana, Cornicabra, Koroneiki, Lechín de Sevilla, Morona,
6 Pajarero, Razzola, Verdial de Huévar, and Villalonga.

7 Other fungal fruit-rot diseases caused by species of *Alternaria*, *Botryosphaeria*,
8 *Fusarium*, and *Phlyctema* occurred in some cultivars during our assessment of
9 anthracnose incidence. The incidence of these diseases was low, however, and therefore
10 did not prevent us from assessing anthracnose incidence, although the time of
11 assessment was longer in trees affected by both anthracnose and some of these diseases.
12 The only exception was cv. Blanqueta, which was severely affected by *Phlyctema*
13 *vagabunda* in some orchards and years. Because symptoms caused by this fungus can
14 be confused with anthracnose, trees severely affected by *P. vagabunda* were excluded
15 from this study.

16 Leaf wilting and branch dieback (BD) are important symptoms associated with
17 olive anthracnose (2, 23). In some countries, such as Greece, Italy, and Portugal, these
18 symptoms have been considered as a primary anthracnose syndrome caused by a direct
19 attack of the pathogen on leaves and branches (13, 33). In Spain, however, BD
20 symptoms have been considered a secondary syndrome resulting from phytotoxins
21 produced in affected fruit (23). In this study, we isolated the pathogen from affected
22 leaves, shoots, and branches of all sampled cultivars, but the percentage of isolations
23 was low (< 3%), supporting the phytotoxin hypothesis. The severity of BD symptoms
24 was assessed only in the La Mina orchard because it was the only orchard with an
25 appropriate number of repetitions (12) for this evaluation. BD symptoms were severe (>

1 75% of the tree canopy affected) on cultivars highly susceptible to fruit rot (Ocal,
2 Picudo, and Hojiblanca) but much less severe (< 10% of the tree canopy affected) on
3 cultivars less susceptible to fruit rot (Razzola, Frantoio, and Leccino). Linear correlation
4 between fruit-rot incidence and BD severity was high ($r = 0.846$, $P < 0.0001$),
5 indicating that susceptibility of olive cultivars to fruit rot and BD is related. Our results
6 also demonstrate that, at least on susceptible cultivars, the damage caused by
7 anthracnose on branches should be considered an important aspect of the disease. In
8 Spain, branch die back has been traditionally ignored, and reductions in fruit yield and
9 oil quality were considered the only harmful effects of olive anthracnose (8, 11, 18).

10 Artificial inoculation of detached fruit has been used to evaluate cultivar
11 susceptibility to anthracnose (12, 18), but discrepancies exist among results from
12 different studies and there was no relationship between artificial inoculations and field
13 observations for some cultivars (2). To clarify these disagreements, we have assessed
14 eleven selected cultivars for their susceptibility to fruit rot using an inoculation method
15 that considers major factors affecting disease severity under controlled conditions (21).
16 Although the progress of disease intensity over time followed a logistic curve for all
17 cultivars, the curves differed substantially among cultivars, and these differences
18 depended on the variable measured: incubation period, AUDPC, ET_{50} , MDRP, and DSI.
19 Linear correlations between disease measured after artificial inoculation and disease
20 incidence in the field were strongest with DSI. DSI (the disease susceptibility index) is
21 an integration of MDRP (the maximum disease progress rate) and ET_{50} (the time
22 required to reach 50% disease intensity). Two cultivars ('Morona' and 'Picudo'),
23 however, showed great discrepancies and had to be eliminated from the correlation
24 analysis. Cultivar Morona was highly susceptible in the field but resistant in artificial
25 inoculations. This difference was due to a misidentification of the cultivar, because

1 'Morona', which was assessed in the field, is different from 'Morona-D', which was
2 assessed in the laboratory (D. Barranco, Universidad de Córdoba, Spain, *personal*
3 *communication*). Similarly, cv. Picudo was very susceptible in the field but only
4 moderately susceptible in artificial inoculations. In this case, the difference was
5 probably due to the use of unripe fruit in the laboratory assay; although the fruit colour
6 (green-yellow) indicated ripening stage 1, the true ripening stage (based on maturity of
7 internal tissues) was probably lower. This was suspected because many inoculated fruit
8 remained green-yellow at the end of the experiment, 84 days after inoculation, when
9 most fruit of the other cultivars had become violet or black (ripening stages 3 or 4).
10 Differences between internal and external fruit ripening stages have been reported for
11 other late-maturing cultivars (1).

12 Results from artificial inoculation confirmed orchard observations and were
13 consistent with the published results for most cultivars (3, 20). However, there were
14 some discrepancies with respect to the reaction of some cultivars under controlled
15 conditions. Mateo-Sagasta (1968), who inoculated non-wounded detached fruit of 26
16 Spanish cultivars, found that cv. Picual was immune, Verdial de Huévar had low
17 susceptibility, and 'Hojiblanca' and 'Lechín de Sevilla' were moderately resistant.
18 These cultivars were more susceptible in our study and in other studies (2, 20, 27) than
19 in Mateo-Sagasta (1968), perhaps because the latter study used olive fruit that were less
20 ripe. That susceptibility of fruit to anthracnose increases with maturity (21) was
21 confirmed by our results for cv. Picual, in which mature black fruit ('Picual-V') were
22 highly susceptible while green fruit ('Picual-G') were moderately resistant. The greater
23 susceptibility of mature fruit may be related to the loss of one or several host resistance
24 mechanisms that are present in immature fruit (26). Although these resistance
25 mechanisms have not been studied for olive anthracnose, higher concentrations of

1 phenolic compounds in immature than mature olive fruits may account for the
2 resistance of immature fruit to several olive pests and diseases (28).

3 Other discrepancies between our results and those published by other researchers
4 using artificial inoculation concern cvs. Frantoio and Leccino, which have been
5 reported as susceptible under artificial inoculation (15) but which were resistant in the
6 current study. This difference could once again be related to the ripeness of the
7 inoculated fruit, because our results and field observations (1, 3) concur on the
8 resistance of both cultivars to anthracnose. Differences in virulence of pathogen
9 populations also could explain some discrepancies for cultivar reaction in different
10 places as has been observed in artificial inoculations (J. Moral, C. J. Xavier, and A.
11 Trapero *unpublished data*).

12 Benlloch (1942) and de Andrés (1991) indicated that late-maturing cultivars are
13 more affected by anthracnose than the earlier-maturing ones. Our study did not
14 demonstrate differences in susceptibility of cultivars associated with the time of
15 ripeness because we found high susceptibility to anthracnose in early-, medium-, and
16 late-maturing cultivars. The higher incidence of anthracnose in late-ripening cultivars
17 was related with the late harvest of these cultivars, while cultivars that ripen early may
18 escape from anthracnose if they are harvested early (4). However, olive growers can use
19 cultivars that ripen more slowly as an avoidance strategy to reduce anthracnose
20 epidemics, and the planting of late-maturing cultivars has been recommended as a
21 control practice (5, 21).

22 The analysis of variance of DSI and the other measures of anthracnose
23 susceptibility, together with the relationship between these variables and field
24 observations and the need to compare our results with published data, led us to place the
25 cultivars into three broad categories: highly susceptible, moderately susceptible, and

1 resistant. According to these categories, the 21 cultivars evaluated in this study should
2 be classified as follows: eight are highly susceptible (Cornicabra, Hojiblanca, Lechín de
3 Sevilla, Manzanilla de Sevilla, Morona, Ocal, Picudo, and Verdial de Huévar), five are
4 moderately susceptible (Arbequina, Arbosana, Morrut, Pajarero, and Villalonga), and
5 eight are resistant (Blanqueta, Empeltre, Frantoio, Koroneiki, Leccino, Morona-D,
6 Picual, and Razzola). Based in our results, cvs. Verdial de Huévar and Picual could be
7 used to separate these categories, in that ‘Verdial de Huévar’ separates highly
8 susceptible from moderately susceptible cultivars, while ‘Picual’ separates moderately
9 susceptible from resistant cultivars. Because cultivar reactions varied continuously from
10 highly susceptible to highly resistant, we found significant differences in susceptibility
11 among cultivars within each category. Still, the simplified classification, with only three
12 categories, will be valuable if included in a database where it can be compared with
13 other published research.

14 Assessments of artificial inoculations of detached fruit complements field
15 assessments to characterize anthracnose susceptibility in olive cultivars. At present, we
16 are using the rating scale and artificial inoculations to assess the entire OGWB and other
17 cultivar trials in southern Spain. These assessment methods could also be used to
18 characterize anthracnose susceptibility of other olive cultivars and genotypes in
19 different collections and breeding programs in the world (3, 27).

20 The use of less susceptible or resistant cultivars is the best way to control many
21 plant diseases. Although this control method has not been considered as a priority for
22 olive anthracnose, it will become more important for newly established plantations with
23 a high density of trees or for hedgerow plantations. These new plantations are more
24 vulnerable to anthracnose epidemics because the high density of trees favors pathogen

1 dispersal and environmental conditions for infection (31). The methods described in this
2 paper will help researchers screen olive cultivars for anthracnose resistance.

3

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1 **Table 1** Rating scale values and average and interval of percentage of olive fruit
 2 affected by anthracnose

Scale value (0-10)	Affected fruit (%) ^a	Interval (%) ^a
0	<0.04	0.00-0.04
1	0.14	0.04-0.23
2	0.41	0.24-0.70
3	1.22	0.71-2.09
4	3.57	2.10-6.02
5	10	6.03-16.13
6	25	16.14-36.60
7	50	36.61-63.39
8	75	63.40-83.86
9	90	83.87-93.97
10	97	93.98-100

3 ^aValues taken from the logistic function $Y = \frac{100}{1+3^{(7-X)}}$ in which Y = percentage of
 4 affected fruit and X = scale value.

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1 **Table 2** Incidence of anthracnose in selected olive cultivars in three experimental orchards during 1997/98, 2005/06, and 2006/2007

Cultivar ^a	Ripeness ^b	Alameda del Obispo			La Mina		Venta del Llano	Average
		1997/98	2005/06	2006/07	2005/06	2006/07	2006/07	
Arbequina	Medium	2.0 de ^c	4.0 cde ^c	3.9 d ^c	0.2 d ^c	2.7 c ^c	0.3 c ^c	2.1
Arbosana	Medium	0.0 e	1.0 fg	3.3 de	-	-	-	1.4
Blanqueta	Medium	1.5 de	1.0 fg	2.0 ef	0.0 d	2.0 c	0.0 c	1.1
Cornicabra	Late	9.0 ab	7.0 ab	9.0 a	-	-	1.0 c	6.5
Empeltre	Early	0.5 de	0.0 g	1.3 fg	-	-	0.0 c	0.5
Frantoio	Early	0.1 e	0.0 g	0.1 g	0.0 d	0.2 d	0.0 c	0.1
Hojiblanca	Late	10.0 a	9.0 a	8.8 a	3.3 ab	7.6 a	4.5 ab	7.2
Koroneiki	Medium	0.5 de	0.0 g	1.0 f	-	-	0.0 c	0.4
Leccino	Early	-	-	-	0.8 cd	2.6 c	0.0 c	1.1
Lechín de Sevilla	Early	8.8 ab	5.0 bcd	7.2 b	-	-	4.0 b	6.3
Manzanilla de Sevilla	Early	9.5 a	6.0 bc	8.7 a	-	-	5.0 ab	7.3
Morona	Late	9.3 a	5.5 bc	9.5 a	-	-	6.0 ab	7.6
Morrut	Late	1.5 c	3.0 def	6.5 b	-	-	0.0 c	2.8
Ocal	Early	10.0 a	8.7 a	9.6 a	4.8 a	9.0 a	6.7 a	8.1
Pajarero	Early	-	-	7.5 b	2.2 bc	3.0 c	1.0 c	3.4
Picual	Early	6.0 c	1.0 fg	5.0 cd	0.2 d	2.9 c	0.0 c	2.5
Picudo	Late	9.8 a	8.3 a	9.5 a	4.4 a	7.9 a	4.0 b	7.3
Razzola	Early	0.5 de	0.0 g	0.0 g	0.0 d	0.2 d	0.0 c	0.1
Verdial de Huévar	Late	7.0 bc	5.0 bcd	6.6 bc	-	-	0.0 c	4.4
Villalonga	Early	-	2.0 efg	5.0 cd	0.4 d	5.2 b	0.0 c	2.5

2 ^aCultivars were grown in three experimental orchards (“Alameda del Obispo”, “La Mina”, “Venta del Llano”) in southern Spain.

3 ^bRipeness time of cultivars in southern Spain (1, 27).

- 1 °Fruit-rot incidence was estimated using a 1-10 rating scale for homogeneity of variance and normality. Means with the same letter are not
- 2 significantly different according to Tukey's HSD test at $P = 0.05$.

1 **Table 3** Disease reaction of selected olive cultivars inoculated with *Colletotrichum acutatum*^a

Cultivar ^b	T ₀ ^c	T ₅₀ ^c	T ₁₀₀ ^c	SAUDPC ^d	ET ₅₀ ^e	MDPR ^e	DSI ^e	ANCOVA ^f
Arbequina	7.0	19.0	47.0	82.8 bc	22.0 fg	5.24 d	0.24 d	79.6 bc
Arbosana	9.8	24.5	50.8	73.8 cd	28.3 ef	6.12 d	0.22 d	42.6 d
Blanqueta	21.5	45.0	72.5	44.6 f	48.4 bc	4.42 d	0.09 de	5.4 fg
Frantoio	25.0	45.5	74.0	42.3 f	49.9 b	6.09 d	0.12 de	4.4 g
Hojiblanca	10.5	12.8	22.3	92.9 ab	15.4 gh	21.65 a	1.41 a	95.6 ab
Koroneiki	15.5	46.0	>84	45.4 ef	49.3 bc	2.42 d	0.05 e	8.1 fg
Morona-D	17.8	35.8	72.5	56.3 e	40.3 cd	4.09 d	0.10 de	10.3 f
Ocal	5.8	9.5	26.8	97.1 a	12.4 h	10.46 c	0.85 b	98.0 a
Picual-G	19.0	38.4	70.0	54.2 e	42.3 bc	4.06 d	0.10 de	24.3 ef
Picual-V	14.8	18.3	34.5	85.1 bc	20.6 fgh	14.72 b	0.72 bc	81.6 bc
Picudo	15.8	25.5	56.8	69.1d	31.6 de	5.56 d	0.18 d	31.7 de
Razzola	50.3	80.5	>84	8.0 g	80.8 a	3.01 d	0.04 e	0.05 h
Verdial	15.0	19.8	35.5	81.3 bc	23.1 efg	12.95 bc	0.56 c	73.6 cd

2 ^aDetached fruit were sprayed with a conidial suspension (10⁵ conidia/ml) and incubated in humid chambers at 23 ± 2°C for 84 days. There were
3 100 inoculated fruit per cultivar. Controls were inoculated with water and remained disease free (data not shown).

4 ^dDetails of cultivars are in Table 1. ‘Morona-D’ is an unknown cultivar that was initially identified as ‘Morona’. ‘Picual-G’ and ‘Picual-V’ are
5 two samples of the same cultivar differing in the ripening stage of the fruit when they were inoculated: green-yellow (G) and violet (V).

6 ^eDisease development times: days from inoculation to the following three disease intensity index (DII) values: DII > 0 (T₀), DII = 50% (T₅₀), and
7 DII = 100% (T₁₀₀). DII values were obtained by data interpolation.

1 ^dStandardized Area Under Disease Progress Curve calculated by trapezoidal integration of DII values expressed as percentage of a maximum
2 theoretical curve.

3 ^eParameters derived from the logistic regression of DII over time: mean period for disease development or inflexion point of the logistic curve
4 (ET₅₀), maximum disease progress rate (MDPR), and disease susceptibility index (DSI) calculated as $DSI = MDR/T_{50}$.

5 ^fMeans of DII estimated by analysis of covariance using time as a covariable. DII data were transformed by the logit function $\left[\ln\left(\frac{DII}{100 - DII}\right) \right]$ for
6 analysis.

7 ^gFor each column, means with the same letter are not significantly different according to Tukey's HSD test at $P = 0.05$.

8

1 **Table 4** Correlation between the average of anthracnose incidence for twelve olive
 2 cultivars in three experimental orchards and disease severity variables in detached olive
 3 fruit of the same cultivars artificially inoculated with *Colletotrichum acutatum*

Disease variable ^a	All cultivars		Without ‘Morona’ and ‘Picudo’	
	r ^b	P ^b	r ^b	P ^b
SAUDPC	0.6633	0.0187	0.8103	0.0045
ET ₅₀	- 0.6519	0.0216	- 0.7827	0.0074
MDPR	0.5309	0.0758	0.8053	0.0049
DSI	0.6021	0.0383	0.9046	0.0003
ANCOVA	0.5662	0.0549	0.8833	0.0007

4

5 ^aParameters used to characterize disease intensity on detached olive fruit artificially
 6 inoculated with *C. acutatum*: standardized area under disease progress curve
 7 (SAUDPC), estimated time to reach 50% of disease intensity index (ET₅₀), maximum
 8 disease progress rate (MDPR), disease susceptibility index (DSI = MDPR / ET₅₀), and
 9 mean of disease intensity index estimated by analysis of covariance (ANCOVA).

10 ^bCorrelation coefficient (*r*) and probability value (*P* value) using the Pearson’s
 11 correlation test.

12

1 **LEGEND TO THE FIGURES**

2

3 **Figure 1** Relationship between the percentages of olive fruit affected by anthracnose (Y)
4 and rating scale values (X , 0-10). Curves were generated by the logistic function
5 $Y = \frac{100}{1 + 3^{(7-X)}}$. Dotted lines represent the interval in the percentage of affected fruit per
6 each scale value (see Table 1).

7

8 **Figure 2** Relationship between the observed (counts) and the estimated (logistic
9 transformation) values of the percentage of fruit affected by anthracnose. **A)** Percentage
10 of affected fruit observed by counts over rating scale values. Line represents the logistic

11 function $Y = \frac{100}{1 + 3^{(7-X)}}$ relating rating scale values (X) with percentage of affected fruit

12 (Y). **B)** Linear regression of percentage of affected fruit observed by counts over
13 percentage estimated by the logistic function. A total of 55 trees, five per each scale
14 value, were assessed by counting the affected fruit in a random sample of 2500 fruit per
15 tree.

16

17 **Figure 3** Linear correlation between incidence of fruit rot and severity of branch
18 dieback symptoms in eleven olive cultivars grown in the La Mina orchard. Symbols
19 represent the mean of twelve repetitions of each cultivar.

20

21 **Figure 4** Disease progress in detached olive fruit of twelve cultivars inoculated with
22 *Colletotrichum acutatum*.

23

1 **Figure 5** Linear correlation between the average anthracnose incidence in ten olive
2 cultivars grown in three experimental orchards and the disease susceptibility index
3 (DSI) in inoculated fruit. Disease incidence in the orchard was estimated using the
4 rating scale 0 to 10. DSI for artificially inoculated fruit was calculated from the logistic
5 curve of disease intensity index over time.

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Figure 1

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Figure 2

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Figure 3

Figure 4

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Figure 5